

IMPACT OF MGNREGA ON ERADICATION RURAL POVERTY: A STUDY IN DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT OF KARNATAKA

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ABSTRACT:

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) was passed by the Government of India in 2005. The Act guarantees 100 days of wage employment in a financial year to rural household members who are willing to do unskilled manual work. MGNREGA was helpful in poverty reduction and stabilising the Indian economy. The MGNREGA provides empowerment to socially deprived groups, especially women, Scheduled Castes (SCs), and Scheduled Tribes (STs). It also strengthens decentralized, participating planning through the convergence of several anti-poverty and livelihoods initiatives. MGNREGA not only provides employment to the unskilled people in rural areas, but also helps in creating awareness among them about the banking business, the facilities available there through continuous contact with the panchayat, and the programs undertaken by the government for poverty alleviation. It thereby plays an important role in increasing their participation rate in economic activities. This is helping to improve their standard of living by increasing their sources of income as well as improving their daily activities. The present study conducted in the Dakshina Kannada district of Karnataka; the study involved over 100 rural households across the district. It has examined the impact of MGNREGA on the rural deprived who are mainly comprised of small and marginal farmers & agricultural labourers. MGNREGA has helped improve the socio-economic status of small and marginal farmers, landless agricultural laborers and the unskilled people in rural areas by providing them with 100-day employment guarantee and create source of income. Before this all of them lived a lowly life with no work to do and no source of income. Through this MGNREGA program is helpful in eradicating poverty in rural areas as well as improving their socio-economic standard of living. And also, the creation of sustainable rural infrastructure which is expected to foster rural economic growth. Finally, the MGNREGA has a huge impact on the employment structure of rural it helps to reduced poverty and prevented people from falling into poverty.

Keywords: MGNREGA, Employment, Rural Poverty.

INTRODUCTION

MGNREGA was helpful in poverty reduction and stabilising the Indian economy. The MGNREGA provides empowerment to socially deprived groups, especially women, Scheduled Castes (SCs), and Scheduled Tribes (STs). It also strengthens decentralized, participating planning through the convergence of several anti-poverty and livelihoods initiatives. MGNREGA not only provides employment to the unskilled people in rural areas, but also helps in creating awareness among them about the banking business, the facilities available there through continuous contact with the panchayat, and the programs undertaken by the government for poverty eradication. It thereby plays an important role in increasing their participation rate in economic activities. This is helping to improve their standard of living by increasing their sources of income as well as improving their daily activities. The MGNREGA was initiated with the objective of “enhancing livelihood security in rural areas

by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a fiscal year, to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work”. MGNREGA Aims to reduce poverty by providing extra work for those who need it, while also providing empowerment and insurance when other sources of work dry up.

As a great leap forward towards the eradication of poverty in 2005, MGNREGA was implemented by the government of India with the aim of ‘Right to Work’, appropriately controlling the causes of poverty and finally benefitting the bottom class deprived of education, land, skills and social support – whose primary form of employment as the seasonal farming labourers during the cultivation and unemployed for rest of the year or roped to work as migrant labourers wherein females are prescribed to carry with the household chores of dominant class. As a tectonic shift, MGNREGA guarantees 100 days of employment and payment within 15 days in a fiscal year. While the world was faced with unprecedented 2008 global crisis, haunting the entire global states with negative growth, unemployment, widening economic inequalities, in contrast, India was prospering and narrowing down the disparities. MGNREGA was instrumental in poverty reduction and stabilising the Indian economy.

MGNREGA known to be an antidote to poverty, has wider socio-economic prospects. The scheme impetuses significant social change, espousing social harmony and inclusive participatory, with the objective of empowerment. Proviso of the MGNREGA guarantees one third of its job to women, overwhelmingly. In practice, more than half of the participants are women. In FY 22-23 57.40%, FY 21-22 54.82%, FY 20-21 53.19% are women. Total number of women getting exposed to an employment opportunity has a significant impact on social participation which optimises role in decision making, enhances education, stretches the marital age. It also clearly multiplies households’ savings which results in better micro finance management. Duly complementing the idea of participatory democracy, MGNREGA increased Dalit and tribal participation in FY 22-23 37.19%, FY 21-22 37.5%, FY 20-21 38%. Eventually ensuring self-reliance, there was a great deal of rural infrastructure development, creating various natural resources such as ponds, dug wells, horticulture plantations, vermicomposting pits; mutually enhancing the biodiversity and sustainable development. Until 2019, more than 3.61 crores have been geo-tagged under MGNREGA and 7.32 crores worth of assets have been created under NREGA.

MGNREGA reduced poverty by up to 32 per cent and prevented 14 million people from falling into poverty, a study by the National Council of Applied Economic Research (NCAER) and University of Maryland using data from 26,000 rural families through two rounds of survey conducted in 2004-5 and 2011-12 found. MGNREGA also protects the poor from sliding additional into poverty during droughts and floods. It offers an additional 50 days’ work during natural calamities like floods and drought, making it a climate-responsive instrument.

A 2017 survey by the International Institute for Environment and Development (IIED) in Sikkim, Odisha, Andhra Pradesh and Jharkhand found that MGNREGA increased the capacity of people to deal with drought, floods and cyclones. New employment skills related to the creation of infrastructure resulted in a more diversified and specialised workforce that is better able to manage climate-induced hazards.

OBJECTIVE OF THE ACT

- ❖ The objective of the Act is to enhance livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work.

MGNREGA GOALS

- ✓ Strong social safety net for the susceptible groups by providing a fall-back employment source, when other employment alternatives are scarce or inadequate
- ✓ Growth engine for sustainable development of an agricultural economy. Through the process of providing employment on works that address causes of chronic poverty such as drought, deforestation and soil erosion, the Act seeks to strengthen the natural resource base of rural livelihood and create durable assets in rural areas. Effectively implemented, MGNREGA has the potential to transform the geography of poverty
- ✓ Empowerment of rural poor through the processes of a rights-based Law
- ✓ New ways of doing business, as a model of governance reform anchored on the principles of transparency and grass root democracy Thus, MGNREGA fosters conditions for inclusive growth ranging from basic wage security and recharging rural economy to a transformative empowerment process of democracy

RURAL POVERTY

Rural poverty refers to situations where people living in non-urban regions are in a state or condition of lacking the financial resources and essentials for living. People living in poverty do not have enough money for basic necessities such as food and shelter.

The increasing rural poverty is proving to be a significant barrier on the way of reaching its target for country like India. Rural India mostly depends upon agriculture for a living. But most of the farmers rely on traditional methods of agriculture. With this, the annual production is significantly less, leading to the agriculture sector, which is underdeveloped to provide employment, leading to rural poverty in India. Rural poverty can also be a product of poor infrastructure. Rural areas often lack sufficient roads, which can hinder development and mobility. Without roads, the rural poor are cut off from technological development and emerging markets in more urban areas.

India has an overall population of around 1.4 billion, where more than 900 million people live in rural areas of the country. While the poverty rate is reduced due to governmental support and schemes, various factors such as natural disasters, dependency on agriculture, and high birth rates have added to the extended poverty in rural India that hits around 300 million people. As per the recent reports, 22% of Indians fall below the line of poverty, and that's a huge concern that needs proper attention of all.

MGNREGA AND RURAL POVERTY

The main aims and objective of MGNREGA are to remove rural poverty and generate huge employment in rural areas and to develop rural infrastructure. It is the biggest anti-poverty programme in the world. The MGNREGA provides social protection for the most vulnerable people living in rural India. It also enhances the livelihood security of the rural poor by creating wage employment opportunities. MGNREGA resulted in a hike in wages besides challenging the traditional power equations by allowing low-caste and female labourers to be more assertive about their working conditions. The programme has also improved women's bargaining position within the households. According to the National Multidimensional

Poverty Index, the poverty rate in rural India deteriorated from 32.59% to 19.28% between 2015-16 and 2019-2021.

Here are some ways to reduce rural poverty:

- ❖ Increase the productivity of small-scale farms and improve their access to markets
- ❖ Promote more efficient value chains
- ❖ Create jobs, especially for the youth
- ❖ Encourage economic diversification
- ❖ Invest in people and foster skills that can be used in agricultural and non-agricultural activities

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. Mohammad Taufique (2017) “Assessing the Role of MGNREGA in Alleviating Rural Poverty: A Study of Malda District, West Bengal” This study is based on mainly secondary sources of data obtained from Malda District Collectorate, District Rural Development Agency and District Statistical Handbook. It is evident from the study that about 9,617 persons are working under the MGNREGA scheme in 2010-11 in Malda district. Habibpur block has the highest rank (1,248 person) working under the scheme whereas English Bazar block has recorded lowest number of persons (316 person) working under the same scheme. In the year 2008-2009, the total percentage of BPL people was 34.62 per cent while in the year 2010-11 it was reduced to 31.26 per cent. It revealed that MGNREGA has some pioneer role in reducing the rural poverty in Malda district. MGNREGA is not the only welfare initiative scheme but equally an important development effort that could play a bigger role in changing the current phase of rural poverty into a new prosperity.

Garima Meena (2021) “MGNREGA's Contribution to Job Creation and Poverty Eradication in Rural Areas” This research focuses on the MGNREGA's effectiveness in decreasing poverty by identifying the advantages and obstacles associated with its implementation. The study indicates that the MGNREGA scheme has decreased poverty in the study area by offering improved work opportunities. To improve the livelihoods of rural poor people, and people have a positive impression of MGNREGA's performance. As a result, this initiative had a good influence on women's and SC/ST engagement. It may be inferred that the program's goal of giving work to the most disadvantaged members of society has been met.

RESEARCH GAP

MGNREGA not only provide wage employment as an alternative source of livelihood but also create durable assets such as road construction, land development, water conservation and irrigation facility, which has tremendous influence on different sectors of village economy. There are a good number of studies, explaining Role and performance of MGNREGA in sustainable development in Rural India. The literature survey revealed some of the study was related to Income and employment generation under MGNREGA, Impact of MGNREGA in rural development there are only few studies focused on Impact of MGNREGA on eradication Rural Poverty. Thus, the review of literature clearly shows that there is dearth of studies relating to Impact of MGNREGA on eradication Rural Poverty. Hence the present study makes an attempt to explore Impact of MGNREGA on eradication Rural Poverty in study area and also identify the Impact of MGNREGA on eradication Rural Poverty in of in Dakshina Kannada District of Karnataka.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

1. To identify the effect of MGNREGA on livelihood conditions of the respondents in study area.
2. To examine the approach and satisfaction of the respondents for work in MGNREGA in Dakshina Kannada District.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

The following hypothesis have been framed in the present study

- There is increasing trends in Works under MGNREGA at study area.
- There is positive mean impact score (Mean satisfaction score) of MGNREGA on Employment, Income earning, Standard of living, savings, and Social Participation at study area

METHODOLOGY

The present study is on empirical investigation based on sample interview of beneficiary of MGNREGA. The present study is based on both primary and secondary data and a systematic random sampling technique has been adopted for survey. The primary data has collected from many villages in Dakshina Kannada District in Karnataka State. Where large numbers of beneficiary of MGNREGA in Dakshina Kannada district of Karnataka. Majority of the people in this area are economically weak and are lead poor standard of living. The survey has been conducted by taking 100 beneficiaries of MGNREGA in the study area and respondents are randomly selected who are worked in MGNREGA scheme. Secondary data collected from Various Books, Newspapers, journals, the MGNREGA website. Simple tables, percentage method is used to analyses the data, and have been depicted by simple chart.

MGNREGA is a revolutionary step for India's poor in alleviating their poverty. The act NREGA came into force in 2006. Initially, 200 districts were selected for the enforcement of the scheme. But in the year 2008, it was implemented in all 640 districts of the country. The main aims and objective of MGNREGA are to remove rural poverty and generate huge employment in rural areas and to develop rural infrastructure. It is the biggest anti-poverty programme in the world.

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IMPACT OF MGNREGA ON ERADICATION RURAL POVERTY

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The MGNREGA was introduced with the objective of "enhancing livelihood security in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year, to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work". MGNREGA not only provide wage employment as a substitute source of livelihood but also create durable assets such as road construction, land development, water conservation and irrigation facility, which has tremendous influence on different sectors of village economy. Employment is to be provided within 5 km of an applicant's residence, and minimum wages are to be paid.

FEATURES OF MAHATMA GANDHI NATIONAL RURAL EMPLOYMENT GUARANTEE ACT (MGNREGA)

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA) provides many benefits to rural communities in India. Some of the main features of MNREGA scheme are as follows:

- 1. Employment Opportunities:** MNREGA guarantees a minimum of 100 days of wage employment per year to rural households, providing a reliable source of income and reducing unemployment.
- 2. Poverty Alleviation:** By providing employment and income support, MNREGA helps reduce poverty and improve the livelihoods of rural families.
- 3. Asset Creation:** MNREGA emphasizes the creation of durable community assets such as roads, water conservation structures and irrigation facilities, which contribute to long-term development and infrastructure improvements.
- 4. Women Empowerment:** The scheme promotes women's participation in rural employment, empowers them economically and socially and reduces gender inequalities.
- 5. Social Inclusion:** MNREGA targets marginalized sections of the society, including Scheduled Castes (SC) and Scheduled Tribes (ST), promoting social inclusion and reducing socio-economic disparities.
- 6. Environmental Conservation:** MNREGA encourages activities like afforestation, soil and water conservation and renewable energy promotion, contributing to environmental sustainability and natural resource management.
- 7. Skill Development:** The scheme provides an opportunity to unskilled workers to gain experience and develop new skills, enhancing their employability and future prospects.
- 8. Transparency and Accountability:** MNREGA incorporates social audit and grievance redressal mechanisms to ensure transparency, accountability and effective utilization of funds.
- 9. Rural Infrastructure Development:** Through the creation of rural infrastructure assets, MNREGA improves connectivity, access to services and overall development in rural areas.
- 10. Seasonal Employment Stabilization:** MNREGA reduces the vulnerability of rural workers to seasonal unemployment and provides a stable income throughout the year.

The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA) is a transformative scheme that has significantly benefited rural communities in India. By providing employment opportunities, poverty alleviation, wealth creation and empowering the marginalized sections of the society, MNREGA has played an important role in improving the livelihood and welfare of rural families. The scheme's focus on social inclusion, environmental protection, skill development and rural infrastructure development has contributed to sustainable development and inclusive growth. As India strives for rural development and poverty alleviation, MNREGA is a powerful tool to achieve these objectives and create a more equitable and prosperous society.

Table 1: Category Wise Registered and Active job card issued in Dakshina Kannada District in 2022-23

Sl. No	Blocs	Number of Job cards		Registered Workers				Number of Active	Active Workers *			
		Applied for	Issued	SCs	STs	Others	Total Workers	Job Cards	SCs	STs	Others	Total Workers
1	BELTANGADI	42914	42908	10185	7357	79513	97055	18727	2368	2096	23	33835
2	BANTVAL	38064	38063	6001	7098	67468	80567	15098	1248	2019	23	26742
3	MANGALORE	9745	9731	1266	502	17830	19598	3553	211	107	57	6086
4	PUTTUR	15186	15182	4120	4381	22736	31237	8357	1379	1927	13	15689
5	SULYA	17781	17777	6197	4348	27514	38059	7980	1529	1515	11	14954
6	KADABA	16220	16218	3904	1313	26738	31955	9291	1497	723	16	18315
7	MUDIBARE	8352	8352	2654	1367	15173	19194	3512	487	463	61	7072
8	MULKI	3612	3610	837	119	5306	6262	1153	94	24	14	1612

9	ULL ALA	10390	103 85	1047	196	185 56	197 99	415 7	213	37	6 5 7 5	682 5
	Total	162264	162 226	36211	266 81	280 834	343 726	718 28	902 6	89 11	1 1 3 1 9 3	131 130

Source: <https://nreganrep.nic.in>

Table 1 Chart 1 and 2 shows that List of beneficiaries are register with MGNREGA scheme in Dakshina Kannada district in 2022-23. Dakshina Kannda District have 9 taluks, 162264 of them are Applied for job card, 162226 job card are issued to beneficiaries. Out of total beneficiaries 3280834 of them belongs to OBC, 36211 of them belongs to SC, 26681 of them are ST. And There is 71828 Active Job cards and 131130 Active Workers. In total Active Workers. Out of total beneficiaries 113193 of them belongs to OBC, 9026 of them belongs to SC, 8911 of them are ST.

Table 2: Financial Performance Under MGNREGA in Dakshina Kannada District during the Financial Year 2022-2023 (RS. in Lakhs)

Sl · N	Block	Cumulative Expenditure	
		Actual Expenditure	Administration Expenditure

o		On Unskilled Wage	On Semi-skilled and Skilled Wage	On Material	Tax	Rec Exp	Non-Rec Exp	Total Adm. Exp	Total
1	BANTVAL	871.79	1.98	498.54	25.87	0.88	0	0.88	1399.07
2	BELTANGADI	1207.77	14.75	392.91	24.67	3.58	0.7	4.28	1644.38
3	KADABA	802.66	7.11	335.17	11.02	2.57	0	2.57	1158.54
4	MANGALORE	224.87	2.47	158.93	8.28	0.09	0.8	0.88	395.44
5	MUDUBIDARE	271.79	2.86	155.82	9.24	0.07	0.69	0.75	440.46
6	MULKI	65.7	0.65	76.94	4.74	0	0.25	0.25	148.3
7	PUTTUR	638.49	20.27	248.6	14.88	2.09	0	2.09	924.33
8	SULYA	532.02	4.06	212.5	2.48	1.34	0	1.34	752.4
9	ULLALA	220.96	0	209.16	10.2	0	0.85	0.85	441.16
	Total	4836.06	54.16	2288.57	111.39	10.62	3.28	13.89	7304.07

Source: <https://nreganarep.nic.in>

Table 2 shows that Financial Performance Under MGNREGA Total expenditure is 730407 Lakhs in Dakshina Kannada District during the Financial Year 2022-2023 (RS. in Lakhs). Out of total expenditure 483606 lakhs expend on Unskilled Wage and 228857 lakhs on Material only 54.16 lakhs on Semi-skilled and Skilled Wage.

Table 3: Category wise Analysis of Work under MGNREGA at Dakshina Kannada District (Expenditure in lakhs RS)

Sl.No	Work Category Name/Work Sub Category Name/Work Type	Total Works	Ongoing Works	Completed Works	Expenditure
PUBLIC WORKS RELATING TO NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT					
1	Water Conservation	1031	118	172	87.54
2	Watershed management	270	51	31	32.25
3	Irrigation	448	122	64	108.94
4	Traditional water bodies	301	89	48	56.35
5	Afforestation	1123	197	225	157.26
6	Land development	490	46	61	42.17

	Sub Total	3663	623	601	484.51
INDIVIDUAL ASSETS FOR VULNERABLE SECTIONS (ONLY FOR HOUSEHOLDS IN PARAGRAPH 5)					
7	Improving productivity of lands	2430	653	408	241.78
8	Improving livelihoods through	22118	7306	8767	2246.04
9	Development of fallow/waste lands	3756	1550	995	602.13
10	Construction of house	7115	3697	1646	728.53
11	Promotion of livestock	8702	2738	2762	588.36
12	Promotion of fisheries	28	6	7	0.51
	Sub Total	44149	15950	14585	4407.35
COMMON INFRASTRUCTURE FOR NRLM COMPLIANT SELF-HELP GROUPS					
13	Agriculture productivity	59	10	12	7.6
14	Common work-sheds for livelihood activities of self-help groups	15	6	2	42.2
	Sub Total	74	16	14	49.8
RURAL INFRASTRUCTURE					
15	Rural sanitation	10366	2773	3803	485.47
16	Road connectivity/Internal roads/Streets	2168	557	367	944.43
17	Play fields	401	93	57	121.68
18	Disaster preparedness/Restoration	1882	387	402	350.73
19	Construction of building	291	129	54	406.63
20	Food Grain storage structures	60	14	10	26.27
21	Production of building material required for construction	17	1	1	0
22	Maintenance	51	3	3	1.49
23	Any other works	142	2	0	0.05
	Sub Total	15378	3959	4697	2336.75
	Grand Total	63264	20548	19897	7278.41

Source: <https://nreganarep.nic.in>

Table 3 explained that Category wise Analysis of Assets Creation Work under MGNREGA at Dakshina Kannada District in 2022-23. Irrigation and Flood management works, Agricultural and Livestock related works, Fisheries and works in coastal areas and the Rural Drinking water and Sanitation related works. Total expenditure for completed work was 7278.41 lakhs in 2022-22. It is greater than previous year. It clearly shows that there is in increasing trends in expenditure on Work under MGNREGA.

SURVEY BASED ANALYSIS AND DATA INTERPRETATION

Dakshina Kannada (South Canara) is the southern coastal district of Karnataka State with an area of 4859 Sq. km. The district is bound by sea in the west and Western Ghats in the East, Udupi district in the North and Kerala State in the South. A survey of 100 MGNREGA

beneficiary from many villages of Dakshina Kannada district of Karnataka state has been conducted of 100 MGNREGA beneficiary have been interviewed through questionnaire. The research findings are as follows,

Table 4: Distribution of Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Rank
Male	64	1
Female	36	2
Total	100	

Source: - Primary data

Table 4 show that out of the total 60 respondents are male and 40 are female. The MGNREGA provides empowerment to socially deprived groups, especially women without any discrimination in Wages.

Table 5: Age of Respondent.

Sl. No	Age group	Frequency	Rank
1.	Below 25 years	10	4
2.	25-30 years	32	2
3.	35-40 years	36	1
4.	45-50 years	16	3
5.	51 and above	08	5
	Total	100	

Table 5 shows that 10 respondents are in age group below 25 years, 32 of respondents are in the age group of 25-30 years, 36 of the respondents are come 35 to 40 years age group, 16 of the respondents are come under Below 45-50 years age category, and only 08 of the responded 51 and above years.

MARITAL STATUS

Marital status is also a social pointer for considerate the socio-economic status of beneficiary.

Table 6: Marital Status of Respondent.

Sl. No	Marital status	Frequency	Rank
1.	Married	75	1
2.	Unmarried	04	3
3.	Widow	14	2
4.	Divorced/separated	07	4
	Total	100	

Source: - Primary data

Table 6 shows that out of 75 respondents of them are found to be married, 4 Unmarried, 14 widowed and only 7 of them are divorced. Nowadays Married and widowed/divorced people get different treatments in the society MGNREGA can helps to them create their individual life

EDUCATION STATUS

The education is an important right that provides opportunities for socio-economic uplift. In India many reasons related with not educating rural people.

Table 7: Educational Status of Respondent.

Sl. No	Level of Education	Frequency	Rank
1.	Illiterate	16	1
2.	Primary	40	2
3.	High school	28	3
4.	PUC	12	4
5.	UG and above	04	6
	Total	100	

Source: - Primary data

Table 7 reveals that 16 of respondents were observed to be illiterates followed by primary 40%, High school 28%, Pre university 12%, under graduate and above only 4. Among rural community school dropout is very common both boy and girls

IMPACT ON LEVEL OF INCOME:

The more visible positive impact of MGNREGA beneficiary is observed in the form of increase in level of income after joining the MGNREGA. Our observation on the basis of sample is presented below.

Table 8: MGNREGA Beneficiary Income Position after Joining MGNREGA.

S.No	Income of Beneficiary	Income Before join	Income After
1.	No income	24	00
2.	Up to 20000	34	08
3.	20000 to 40000	16	30
4.	40000 to 60000	12	14
5.	60000 to 80000	08	12
6.	80000 to 100000	04	16
7.	100000 and above	02	20
	Total	50	50

Source: - Primary data

In table no 8 we observe following changes in the income of the MGNREGA beneficiary as result of joining the MGNREGA.

- ❖ After becoming the MGNREGA beneficiary the average earning has increased, particularly 12 respondents without income before become the beneficiary, after the got job in MGNREGA 20 members have become wage earners.
- ❖ The income of the MGNREGA beneficiary have widened during the period under study as reflected in increase variance.
- ❖ MGNREGA beneficiary were benefited positively in terms of finding better opportunity of income. But the activities in which they have joined who have benefited differently due to their skill, initial capital and knowledge about the opportunities.

Table 9: Distribution of Factor Influenced Involved in MGNREGA

Characteristics		Frequency	Rank
Occupation	Agriculture	35	02
	Agriculture and agricultural labourer	40	01
	agricultural labourer	25	03
Land Holding	Below 2.5 Acre	50	01
	2.5 to 5 acres	40	02
	Above 5 acres	10	03
Years of experience in MGNREGA	Up to 5 years	30	02
	5 to 10 years	48	01
	10 to 15 years	22	03
Share of annual Income from MGNREGA	Less than 15K	30	02
	15 to 30K	40	01
	30 to 45K	20	03
	45k and above	10	04
Participation in Social Life	No. Membership in any institute	50	01
	Membership of Gram panchayat	09	04
	Membership in Dairy	20	02
	Women Mandal	10	03
	SDMC Member	04	06
	Membership in cooperative societies	07	05

Source: - Primary data

35 of responds are depend on only in agriculture, 40 of them doing Agriculture and agriculture laborer, and 25 of respondents depending on only agriculture laborer.

50 % of respondents having below 2.5 acre of land, 40% of them having 2.5 to 5 acres, 10% of them have Above 5 acres.

48% of the having 5 to 10 years of experience in MGNREGA, 22% of them having 10 to 15 years of experience, and 30%of them having up to 5years of experience in MGNREGA.

05% of respondent's family income Less than 2lak, 30% of them have 2 to 4 lakhs, 40% of them have 4 to 5lakhs and 25% of them have 5 lakhs and above family income per year.

30% of respondents got Less than 15K in their total income from only MGNREGA scheme, 40% of them got 15 to 30K, 20% of them got 30 to 40K from MGNREGA scheme total family income. Only 10% of them earned 45k and above.

MGNREGA beneficiary have resulted not only at individual level but at the social level also. The process of economic liberalization has improved the level of income and so also their economic status and participation in social life. It is presented in the following table.

After joining the MGNREGA beneficiary extended to the membership of other institutes. In this regard we observed following trends.

- ❖ The participation in local government bodies such as village panchayat. From the sample members 50% members have not befitted in terms of participation in other institutes. But 50 % members have got opportunity to participate in other institutes.
- ❖ The joining in local government bodies is a remarkable benefit as it influences the status and moral of the other women.

The increase in institutional participation helps the rural people to play an active and decisive role. The overall economic and social conditions of people have improved after becoming the MGNREGA beneficiary

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypothesis have been framed in the present study

H1: There is increasing trends in Works under MGNREGA at study area.:

Table 10: Trends of Works under MGNREGA at Dakshina Kannada District from 2014-15 to 2023-24 (Expenditure in lakhs RS)

Sl.No	Years	Total Works	Ongoing Works	Completed Works	Expenditure
1.	2014-15	10354	3295	6993	1156.96
2.	2015-16	15307	9931	5308	2001.37
3.	2016-17	26732	16229	10033	5208.35
4.	2017-18	34917	17416	14082	5200.43
5.	2018-19	36987	18937	11358	5160.62
6.	2019-20	36682	15827	11881	5707.16
7.	2020-201	43755	21701	9291	6215.69
8.	2021-22	58364	21711	18952	7016.94
9.	2022-23	63264	20548	19897	7278.41
10.	2023-24	60854	15340	17482	5277.36
	Mean	38721.6	16093.5	12527.7	5022.329
	AGR	23.93	9.81	18.39	26.77
	CAGR	19.38	16.63	9.60	16.17
	Standard Deviation	18323.3	5726.28	4986.452	1977.07

Source: <https://nreganarep.nic.in>

Table 10 and chart 3 shows that Trends of Works under MGNREGA at Dakshina Kannada District from 2014-15 to 2023-24. It is clearly state that there is increasing trends in expenditure on Works under MGNREGA. From 2014-15 to 2023-24 mean expenditure is 5022.32, AGR is 26.77, CAGR is 16.17 and Standard deviation is 1977.07.

H2: There is positive mean impact score (Mean satisfaction score) of MGNREGA on Employment, Income earning, Standard of living, savings, and Social Participation at study area

Table 11: Derivation of mean impact score (Mean satisfaction score) of MGNREGA on Employment, Income earning, Standard of living, and saving, and Social Participation.

		Degree of Impact				
		Negative Impact	No Impact	Good Impact	Substantia I Impact	Total
Impact Score		-1	0	1	2	
Impact on Employment	NO of Respondents	0	05	30	65	100 (A)
	Cumulative Score	0 (0*-1)	0 (0*05)	30(1*30)	130 (2*65)	160 (B)
	Mean impact Score	B/A= 160/100 =1.6				
Impact on Income earning	NO of Respondents	0	10	40	50	100 (A)
	Cumulative Score	0 (0*-1)	0 (0*10)	40 (1*40)	100 (2*50)	140 (B)
	Mean impact Score	B/A= 140/100 =1.4				
Impact on standard of living	NO of Respondents	0	06	45	49	100 (A)
	Cumulative Score	0 (0*-1)	0 (0*06)	45 (1*45)	98 (2*49)	143 (B)
	Mean impact Score	B/A= 143/100 =1.43				
Impact on saving	NO of Respondents	0	35	60	05	100 (A)
	Cumulative Score	0 (0*-1)	0 (0*25)	60 (1*60)	10 (2*05)	70 (B)
	Mean impact Score	B/A= 70/100 =0.70				
Impact	NO of	0	35	55	10	100

on Social Participation	Respondents					(A)
	Cumulative Score	0 (0*-1)	0 (0*35)	55 (1*55)	20(2*10)	75 (B)
	Mean impact Score	B/A= 75/100 =0.75				

(Source: field survey)

Table 11 revealed that impact score of MGNREGA on Employment, Income earning, Standard of living, saving and social participation of MGNREGA beneficiary. MGNREGA's Impact on Employment is grater comparative to all other impact with 1.6 Mean impact Score. Mean impact Score of Impact on Income earning is 1.4, Mean impact Score of Impact on standard of living is 1.43, Mean impact Score of Impact on saving .70 and Mean impact Score of Impact on social participation .75. All impacts are positive in nature. Finally above table shows that MGNREGA dose positive impact on all above Parameters. It is clear that MGNREGA provided livelihoods support it helps to improving rural livelihoods by providing employment to rural un skilled people. It made a positive impact in generation of employment and reduction of poverty. MGNREGA is critical in reducing rural poverty because it enhances social respect, purchasing power, and decreases the bargaining of moneylenders and landlords.

CONCLUSION

MGNREGA a unique welfare programme aimed at improving rural livelihoods by providing employment to rural un skilled people. It made a positive impact in generation of employment and eradication of poverty. MGNREGA is critical in reducing rural poverty because it enhances social respect, purchasing power, and decreases the bargaining of moneylenders and landlords. On the other side, it improves social and economic infrastructure by offering job opportunities and asset Creation in rural area. In a lean season, the Guarantee employment opportunities given by MGNREGA without discrimination help to avoid migration, which in turn serves to improve rural poverty. Furthermore, the Act is working to improve the livelihoods of rural poor people, and people have a positive impression of MGNREGA's performance. Through this MGNREGA program is helpful in eradicating poverty in rural areas as well as improving their socio-economic standard of living. And also, the creation of sustainable rural infrastructure which is expected to foster rural economic growth. Finaly, the MGNREGA has a huge impact on the employment structure of rural it helps to reduced poverty and prevented people from falling into poverty.

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